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Nonlinear Micro-mechanical Response Of The Fibre-reinforced Polymer Composites

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- ❑ FRP composites consisting of two constituents, i.e. glass or carbon fibres embedded in rigid polymer matrix.
- ❑ Exceptional chemical and physical properties (light weight, high strength, etc).
- ❑ Applications:
 - ❖ aerospace,
 - ❖ civil,
 - ❖ automotive,
 - ❖ marine,
 - ❖ wind turbines,
 - ❖ medical.

❑ Long-term durability of composite structures (hygro-thermo-mechanical)

(Ullah et al., 2015, 2016)

❑ Composite plate

❑ Composite cylinder

(Kaczmarczyk et al., 2016)

- ❑ Multi-scale modelling predict and describe macroscopic material behaviour by considering the mechanics of the **underlying microstructure (RVE)**.
- ❑ A 3D multi-scale computational homogenisation framework is developed for the prediction of nonlinear micro-mechanical response of the FRP composites, including:
 - ❖ Matrix damage,
 - ❖ Fibre-matrix decohesion and
 - ❖ Yarns (fibres) as transversely isotropic materials.
- ❑ Numerical examples:
 - ❖ Unidirectional GFRP,
 - ❖ Plain weave textile composites.

- Matrix is modelled as elasto-plastic material based on the pressure dependent paraboloidal yield criterion (Tschoegl, 1971)

$$f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \sigma_c, \sigma_t) = 6J_2 + 2I_1(\sigma_c - \sigma_t) - 2\sigma_c\sigma_t$$

- where $I_1 = \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\sigma})$ and $J_2 = \frac{1}{2}\boldsymbol{\eta} : \boldsymbol{\eta}$

$$\boldsymbol{\eta} = \text{dev}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}) = \boldsymbol{\sigma} - \frac{1}{3}I_1$$

- Potential function is written as

$$g(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \sigma_c, \sigma_t) = 6J_2 + 2\alpha I_1(\sigma_c - \sigma_t) - 2\sigma_c\sigma_t$$

$$\alpha = \frac{1 - 2\nu_p}{1 + \nu_p}$$

- Exponential hardening law

$$\sigma_t = \sigma_{t_0} + H_t(1 - e^{-n_t\alpha_0}), \quad \sigma_c = \sigma_{c_0} + H_c(1 - e^{-n_c\alpha_1})$$

- Fibre-matrix decohesion is modelled with cohesive elements with linear traction-separation law

$$t = \begin{cases} E_0 \delta & \text{if } \delta < \delta_0, \\ (1 - \omega) E_0 \delta & \text{if } \delta_0 \leq \delta < \delta_{\max}, \quad \delta = \sqrt{\delta_n^2 + \beta(\delta_{s1}^2 + \delta_{s2}^2)} \\ 0 & \text{if } \delta \geq \delta_{\max}, \end{cases}$$

- Penalty stiffness

$$E_0 = \frac{E}{h} \quad \delta_0 = \frac{f_t}{E_0} \quad \omega = \frac{(2G_f E_0 + f_t^2) \kappa}{2G_f (f_t + k E_0)}$$

- Generalised imposition of different RVE boundary conditions (displacement, traction and periodic) (Kaczmarczyk et al., 2008).

- Discretised system of equations

$$\mathbf{K}\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{C}^T \boldsymbol{\lambda} = \mathbf{0}$$

$$\mathbf{C}\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{D}\bar{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}$$

- where $\mathbf{C} = \int_{\Gamma} \mathbf{H}\mathbf{N}^T \mathbf{N} d\Gamma$ and $\mathbf{D} = \int_{\Gamma} \mathbf{H}\mathbf{N}^T \mathbf{X} d\Gamma$

- Homogenised stress $\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \frac{1}{V} \mathbf{D}^T \boldsymbol{\lambda}$

- Additional flexibility:

- ❖ Arbitrary order of approximation (hierarchical basis functions),
- ❖ PETSc and MOAB libraries and
- ❖ Parallel processing.

Validation of Plasticity Model

Matrix only (epoxy resin)

Parameter	Epoxy matrix
Young's modulus [GPa]	3.76
Poisson's ratio	0.39
Plastic Poisson's ratio	0.3
Yield strength in tension [MPa]	29
Yield strength in compression [MPa]	67

Validation of combined model GFRP subjected to transverse tension

Fibre diameter = $5\mu\text{m}$

Fibre volume fraction = 60%

Randomly generated fibres
(Melro et al., 2008)

Parameter	Glass fibres	Epoxy matrix
Young's modulus [GPa]	74	3.76
Poisson's ratio	0.2	0.39
Plastic Poisson's ratio	--	0.3
Yield strength in tension [MPa]	--	29
Yield strength in compression [MPa]	--	67

Elements: 1,499

3,239

13,027

21,140

Validation of combined model GFRP subjected to transverse tension

Parameter	Value
Interface strength [MPa]	50
Fracture energy [J/m ²]	2

Validation of combined model GFRP subjected to transverse tension

Parameter	Value
Interface strength [MPa]	50
Fracture energy [J/m ²]	2,3,4,100

Validation of combined model GFRP subjected to transverse tension

Parameter	Value
Interface strength [MPa]	50, 35, 20, ∞
Fracture energy [J/m ²]	2

Validation of combined model Plain weave textile composite

Yarns fibres volume fraction = 65%
Composite fibres volume fraction = 35%
Plain weave textile composite
(Kollegal et al., 2001)

Yarns

Matrix

Full RVE

Validation of combined model Plain weave textile composite

Parameter	Yarns	Matrix
E_p [GPa]	18.06	3.79
E_z [Gpa]	48.47	-
ν_p	0.34	0.35
ν_{pz}	0.25	-
G_{zp} [Gpa]	5.58	-

Validation of combined model Plain weave textile composite

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G_{zp} [Gpa]	5.58	-

- ❑ A three-dimensional multi-scale computational homogenisation framework is developed for the prediction of nonlinear micro-mechanical response of the FRP composites.
- ❑ Two dominant damage mechanisms, i.e. matrix damage and fibre-matrix decohesion are considered and modelled using a paraboloidal yield criterion and cohesive elements respectively.
- ❑ The correct implementation and performance of the computational framework is demonstrated with numerical examples including parametric study.
- ❑ The developed computational framework have the flexibility of
 - ❑ Arbitrary order of approximation (hierarchic basis functions),
 - ❑ Generalized RVE boundary conditions,
 - ❑ PETSc and MOAB libraries,
 - ❑ Parallel processing.

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